

Site guidelines for multi-purpose GNSS reflectometry stations

The following guidelines are meant for station operators interested in sharing their station installations for multiple purposes, including GNSS reflectometry (GNSS-R). They complement the International GNSS Service (IGS) Site Guidelines. It was started during the 2015-2019 term of the Working Group 4.3.9 on GNSS Reflectometry (GNSS-R), International Association of Geodesy (IAG).¹

1. There should be unobstructed view from the antenna up to the satellites in the sky, for direct signal reception, especially between 5 and 25 degrees of elevation above the horizon (i.e., between zenith angles of 55 and 85 degrees).
 - 1.1. Trees and buildings should be sufficiently distant in the azimuths of interest. For example, a 6-m tree near a 1.5-m antenna should be distant at least $50 \text{ m} \approx (6 \text{ m} - 1.5 \text{ m})/\tan(5^\circ)$. The general formula, $D = \Delta H/\tan(e)$, involves the vertical separation ΔH between antenna and overhead obstructions and the lower limit satellite elevation angle, typically 5° .
2. There should be unobstructed view from the antenna down to the surface (water, soil, snow, etc.), for reception of reflections, especially between 5 and 25 degrees of depression below the horizon (i.e., between zenith angles of 90 and 115 degrees).
 - 2.1. For water level applications, surface visibility is maximized when the antenna is over the water surface, e.g., at a platform or islet inside the water body. The second best location in terms of surface visibility is in the banks immediately facing the water. If equipment protection is advised (from weather, theft, or vandalism), the antenna may be sheltered away from the water, as sensing occurs at slant direction. In this case, the antenna should be installed high enough to guarantee it retains visibility to the water surface. This is especially important in shallow waters, where submerged sand banks and coral reefs might get exposed to air during low tides. For example, if the antenna is $D = 15 \text{ m}$ distant from the water, then it should be at least $H = 7 \text{ m}$ high, to guarantee reception of reflections at 25° satellite elevation upper limit, $H = D \cdot \tan(e)$. Beware small water bodies may not provide sufficient reflection area; in the case above, if the water channel is 20 m wide, then the antenna is only 35 m away from the opposite bank; in this case, the lower limit of 5° will be undermined, as satellite elevation angles smaller than 10° will be mostly out of the water, $e = \arctan(H/D)$. In general, the horizontal distance should be between 2x and 10x the vertical distance, $2 < D/H = \cot e < 10$, for typical satellite elevation angles, $5^\circ - 25^\circ$. (This assessment considers only simple reflection points; for more rigorous reflection zones, see “FFZ” below.)
 - 2.2. For roof-top installations, give preference to side walls and corners, avoiding the middle of the roof.
3. Other reasons for raising the antenna include:
 - 3.1. For roof-top installations, use a pedestal or mount to raise the antenna at least half meter above the building roof, to minimize near-field effects (strong reflections, edge diffraction, snow accumulation, etc.).
 - 3.2. In ground-based installations for soil moisture applications, use a tripod or other monumentation types to raise the antenna at least 1.5 m above the ground, to allow the recording of enough SNR oscillation cycles.
 - 3.3. In ground-based installations for snow depth applications, make the antenna 1.5 meter taller than the highest expected snow depth accumulation.

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4. The GNSS sampling interval should be inversely proportional to the height of the antenna above the surface; a rule of thumb is: 30 seconds for 2 meters, 10 seconds for 5 meters, 1 second for 10 meters (the exact answer depends on the station latitude, as it affects the satellite trajectory in the sky).
5. Visibility should span an azimuthal sector as large as possible, ideally around 180 degrees, at the very least 90 degrees wide.
6. With regards to surface configuration:
 - 6.1. For soil moisture and snow depth sensing, vegetation should be as sparse and as short as possible, preferably grasses or bare ground.
 - 6.2. In the region of interest, the reflecting surface should be as flat as possible; mild slopes and gentle undulations are acceptable.
 - 6.3. Minimize surface roughness, such as rocks over ground and breaking waves on water, as it may restrict the range of useful satellite elevation angles, due to loss of radio-wave coherence.
7. When there is the need for a fence or enclosure around a GNSS site for security or safety reasons, keep it as far as possible and make wires widely spaced, avoiding narrow metal meshes as they may block the propagation of radio waves.
8. Avoid objects (such as masts, sensors, and other antennas) protruding within a 1.5-m radius around the GNSS antenna.
9. Ancillary equipment (solar panels, gear box, supporting measurement tower/mast, etc.) deployed around the antenna should be placed in azimuths towards the nearest geographical pole (e.g., due north of the antenna in northern latitudes), to take advantage of a hole in the sky satellite coverage (35 degrees around the celestial pole) caused by the orbit inclination (55 degrees w.r.t. the equator).
10. An upright antenna (boresight facing zenith) works well for GNSS-R and can be shared with other applications.
11. Antennas with multipath mitigation technology (e.g., choke rings or resistive plane) work well for GNSS-R, as reflections off grazing incidence have similar direction of arrival and polarization compared to the direct propagation wave.
12. Intermittent campaigns are discouraged; continuously operating installations are to be preferred.
13. Disable tracking elevation mask, setting it to zero or even minus 5 degrees, as the low elevation angles are most useful for Reflectometry; furthermore, positioning applications can always apply a higher mask in post-processing.
14. Record other GNSS in addition to GPS if possible, such as GLONASS, etc.
15. Record modernized GPS signals (L2C, L5, L1C) in addition to legacy ones.
16. RINEX files should contain SNR observables, not just signal strength indicators, or else raw binary files should be kept.
17. Version 3 of the RINEX format is strongly recommended, as it stores separately the SNR of each GNSS signal (e.g., S2X vs. S2W or S1C vs. S1P) – version 2 allows only one SNR observable per carrier frequency.
18. Take photographs of the antenna surroundings, at least every 45 degrees in azimuth, as these will guide the definition of a valid reflection mask; consider stitching photos (static panoramas or interactive “photospheres”) or taking photos annotated with azimuth/elevation angles (using, e.g., “Dioptra” Android app).

Further information:

- The horizontal distance to the specular reflection point is given by $D=H/\tan(e)$, in terms of the height of the antenna above the surface (H) and the satellite elevation angle (e).
- The instantaneous reflection footprint may be approximated by the first Fresnel zone (FFZ), an ellipse aligned with the satellite azimuth. Its major and minor semidiameters are,

respectively, $a = b/\sin(e)$ and $b = (\lambda H/\sin(e) + (1/4)\lambda^2/\sin^2(e))^{0.5}$, where λ is the carrier wavelength; the FFZ center is at $R=D+0.5\lambda\cos(e)/\sin^2(e)$, thus offset from the specular point (at D), which coincides with the near focus of the FFZ (Larson & Nievinski, 2013; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10291-012-0259-7>).

- Open source software for SNR-based GNSS-R is available from:

<https://github.com/fgnievinski/mpsim>

<https://github.com/kristinmlarson>

<https://gnss-reflections.org/>